

Exploring the Impact of Bistatic Target Reflectivity in ISAC-Enabled V2V Setup Across Diverse Geometrical Road Layouts

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ABSTRACT Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) is an intriguing emerging research area that combines radar sensing and communication functionalities in a unified platform, capitalizing on shared aspects of signal processing, spectrum utilization, and system design. For sensing applications, the reflectivity of objects between Transmitter (Tx) and Receiver (Rx) is crucial. It is normally modeled as a uniform scatterer or a group of uniform scatterers in wireless channels. These models do not take into account the dependence of reflectivity on the aspect angles of incident and scattering waves, the composed material, and the geometry of the objects. Therefore, we model the reflectivity of target vehicles using their bistatic Radar Cross Section (RCS), as in radar sensing, within a Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) setup under the ISAC framework. Moreover, we consider constant and variable bistatic Target Reflectivity (TR) integrated setups with two diverse traffic scenarios. These traffic scenarios are modeled to be realistic, with diverse geometrical road layouts, variable vehicle velocities, distinct vehicle positions, and the presence of Diffuse (DI) scattering components. Then, we inspect the impact of the bistatic TR on the behavior of the wireless channel and target detection capability. The variable TR integrated setup leads to a more accurate realization of the scenario, leading to outcomes that closely resemble real-world conditions. The results show the substantial impact of the geometrical setup on the distribution of TR, which emphasizes the need to integrate TR into ISAC-enabled V2V channel models.

INDEX TERMS Autonomous driving, channel models, radar cross-section, radar sensing, radar clutter, signal processing algorithms, vehicle-to-vehicle communication

I. INTRODUCTION

NEXT-GENERATION wireless networks (beyond 5G and 6G) are anticipated to play a pivotal role in enabling a wide range of emerging applications. Such emerging applications not only require high data rates and reliability but also need robust sensing capability. It is anticipated that sensing will play an even more crucial role in these emerging technologies than it did in the past [1]. However, existing dedicated designs for communication and sensing cannot simultaneously meet these modern emerging technologies' data rate and reliability requirements. Moreover, spectrum

scarcity is another challenge in meeting the spectrum-hungry needs of modern emerging technologies [2].

Over the years, wireless communications and radar sensing have advanced in their respective domains with little to no overlap. However, both technologies share many underlying similarities such as signal processing algorithms, propagation medium and mechanisms, devices, and to a certain extent hardware architecture [3]. The ultimate goal of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) is to unify radar sensing and wireless communication operations under a single platform. The aim of ISAC systems is to explore

direct trade-offs and optimize the mutual performance gains of radar sensing and wireless communication [1]. In recent years, the field of ISAC has gained the attention of academia and industry due to its numerous advantages over traditional radar sensing and wireless communication modes. ISAC can significantly improve spectrum utilization and mitigate the spectrum conflict between radar and wireless communication systems. By integrating the radar sensing and communication functionalities within a single device or network infrastructure, ISAC helps reduce hardware size, lower signal processing costs, and improve energy consumption [4], [5]. ISAC is envisioned to play a critical role in various industrial applications, including vehicular networks, indoor localization, Autonomous Driving (AD), and drone networks [6].

One of the most vital applications of ISAC lies within the vehicular environment. The ISAC-enabled Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) setup represents a very challenging application scenario that is essential for the future Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). It is possible to utilize the currently deployed Road Side Units (RSUs) for radar sensing with only minor modifications to the hardware and communication strategies. This adaptation allows ISAC to connect vehicles with one another, as well as with infrastructure and networks. ISAC-enabled V2V setup can lead to more reliable position information and better communication quality which results in improved traffic scenarios (fewer traffic jams, decreased rates of accidents) [7], [8]. However, ISAC-enabled V2V systems are still in their infancy. A thorough understanding of the propagating characteristics of the radio channel for ISAC-enabled V2V systems is critically important for effective design, performance assessment, and standardization [9].

Over the years, various channel models for the traditional V2V communications have been proposed. These include standardized models such as COST action projects, 3GPP Spatial Channel Model (SCM) [10], WINNER channel models [11], IEEE 802.11n & IEEE 802.16ac [12], [13]. Moreover, extensive measurements have been conducted for channel modeling in various experimental setups including highway, urban, rural, cross-road, and street intersections [14]–[18]. These channel models focus on different aspects of the vehicular environment including antenna placement, radiation patterns, and the polarization of both transmitting and receiving antennas [19]–[22]. However, traditional V2V channel models fail to meet the stringent reliability and accuracy requirements of ISAC-enabled V2V systems.

As radar sensing and wireless communication are integrated into a unified platform, the characteristics of the propagation channel for ISAC-enabled V2V systems are very different than the traditional V2V channels. It involves the signal transmission from communication Transmitter (Tx) to the communication Receiver (Rx) along with echo propagation from sensing Tx to the scatterers to the sensing Rx. This makes ISAC-enabled V2V channels more susceptible to the surrounding environment, including moving vehicles,

pedestrians, and scatterers [23], [24]. The abundance of scatterers in the surrounding environment leads to significant multipath effects and clutter, characterized by a rapid birth and death process. Due to the high-speed mobility of vehicles and scatterers distributions in the environment, time-varying channel behavior must be modeled in ISAC-enabled V2V channels. These factors make channel modeling of ISAC-enabled V2V systems a highly challenging task.

The literature on ISAC channel measurements and models is still limited, primarily focusing on scenarios with little or no mobility, which fail to capture the rapidly varying temporal characteristics of the channel. A vehicular ISAC system based on conventional IEEE 802.11ad standard at 60 GHz is presented in [25]. A Rician channel model is used for communication, while a path-based model is employed for radar sensing. A scatterer-based hybrid channel model framework at 140 GHz is presented in [26]. The reflectivity/scattering of different materials objects is modeled as the exponential functions using measured monostatic Radar Cross Section (RCS). The dependency of RCS on the incident and scattering angles is not considered in [26]. A low complexity Millimeter-Wave (mm-Wave) model of the street canyon scenario is presented in [27] in which, in place of a deterministic propagation model, a statistical distribution of bistatic RCS is used to model vehicles and pedestrians. In [27], a normal distribution of bistatic RCS values is assumed, which may not be true and may lead to less accurate results in real-world scenarios. The bistatic RCS value is drawn from the normal distribution, which lacks the impact of varying incident and scattering angles.

In [28], an ISAC-enabled V2V setup at sub-6 GHz is presented where a two-way highway scenario with multiple target vehicles is presented. Similarly, the model proposed in [28] is further extended in [29] by incorporating various antenna radiation patterns and placement schemes to evaluate the impact of directivity on target detection performance. The directivity of antennas plays a crucial role in distinguishing Target of Interest (TOI) from unwanted clutter. However, in both studies, a constant bistatic RCS value is assumed for target vehicles in the scenario for simplicity. Moreover, all vehicles are assumed to be of the same type and dimensions in both studies. This could result in less accurate outcomes and introduce errors in target detection.

However, in literature for ISAC-enabled V2V channel models, the target is typically assigned with a constant RCS value or drawn from a probability distribution without consideration of the geometrical road layouts and orientation of Tx, Rx, and moving vehicles [26]–[29]. Therefore, this does not reflect a realistic scenario, and variation in Target Reflectivity (TR) is essential for accurate channel performance analysis and target detection accuracy in a clutter-rich environment. This study explores variable TR and provides insights into its importance for realistic and accurate ISAC-enabled V2V channel models. The main contributions of the study are summarized as follows:

- In this study, we investigate the impact of TR on the performance of a bistatic ISAC-enabled V2V system by accounting for vehicle shape and dimensions, road geometry, and the orientation of the Tx, Rx, and moving vehicles. This approach differs from existing literature, where the TR value is typically assumed to be constant or randomly drawn from a probability distribution, which can lead to inaccurate results.
- The bistatic TR of three different vehicle models is simulated as bistatic RCS at 5.9 GHz. The vehicle models selected are commonly found in day-to-day traffic scenarios. This gives us variable TR distributions for different vehicle models adopted. For each vehicle, we have an $M \times N$ RCS matrix with a step size of 0.01° for all possible combinations of incidence and scattering angles.
- The impact of the geometrical road layouts on the variable TR distribution is explored by considering two traffic setups such as 1) a straight road section and 2) a curved road path. Although the same approach can be extended to other geometrical layouts, such as road intersections or T-shaped configurations, this study focuses solely on these two layouts. These specific layouts are chosen as they represent two extreme cases, providing a comprehensive analysis within this scope.
- The variable TR is integrated into the ISAC-enabled V2V channel model. It is shown that the variable TR integrated channel model produces more realistic results. In contrast, the constant TR integrated channel model serves only as an approximation of those results.
- The performance of the variable and constant TR integrated channel models is compared and analyzed. The impact of variable TR on channel magnitude variations is examined, along with its influence on overall channel performance and target detection capability.

A. Notation

Scalars, vectors, matrices, and sets are denoted using different typographical conventions. Scalars are represented by italic letters (a) or Greek letters (α). Vectors are indicated by bold lowercase letters (\mathbf{a}), and matrices are denoted by bold uppercase letters (\mathbf{A}). Matrix operations follow standard mathematical conventions. \mathbf{A}^T and \mathbf{A}^{-1} , represent transpose and inverse of matrix \mathbf{A} , respectively. The Fourier transform operation is denoted by $\mathcal{F}\{\cdot\}$, and its inverse by $\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\cdot\}$. $\mathbf{a} \odot \mathbf{a}$ represents the dot product. Norms and other mathematical notations include the ℓ_2 norm, which is denoted as $\|\mathbf{x}\|_2$ and represents the Euclidean norm of vector \mathbf{x} .

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Sec. II describes the geometrical configurations, vehicle models employed, vehicle routes, and utilized simulation tools. Next, Sec. III discusses bistatic RCS acquisition along with constant and dynamic RCS methodologies. Sec. IV depicts the dynamic RCS integration in the extended ISAC channel

model and signal processing methods adopted for calculating channel magnitude and target detection. Section V presents the simulation results for both constant and dynamic RCS integrated setups, comparing their performance in terms of channel magnitude and target detection capability. The paper concludes with a discussion, and future work is outlined in Section VI.

II. GEOMETRICAL CONFIGURATION, VEHICLE ROUTES AND SIMULATION TOOLS

This section discusses the geometrical configurations adopted for the study. This section also highlights different vehicle models selected for bistatic TR acquisition. Moreover, the vehicles' initial position and followed traffic routes are also described here. This section also explains the distribution of Diffuse (DI) scatterers along the geometrical setups. This section also provides insight into different simulation tools used in our analysis.

A. Geometrical Road Layouts

The adopted geometrical configuration represents two scenarios commonly encountered in a vehicular environment, serving as extreme case studies. The first geometrical setup represents a straight road section similar to a typical highway scenario of 1 km length as shown in Fig. 1. The second setup

FIGURE 1. Straight road section.

models a curved road section, resembling a mountainous region characterized by a winding road with multiple sharp turns as shown in Fig. 2. The chosen length of the curved road section is also 1 km. We considered a 6-lane (3-lanes per direction) arrangement for both geometrical setups. The width of the road is 27 m with a lane width of 4.5 m. On both sides of the road, the DI scattering components representing vegetation, point scatterers, and points of reflection beyond the road, are considered to evaluate their impact on channel performance and target detection. The width of the DI scattering region is 5 m on both sides of the road. We considered a boundary region of $d_{\text{gap}} = 3.75$ m between the start of the DI scattering region and the boundary of the outermost lanes (L-0, RL-0). The distance from the center

FIGURE 2. Curved road section.

of the road to the first DI scattering component is 17.25 m. The x and y coordinates of the DI scatterers are modeled by a uniform distribution as given in (1):

$$(x_{diff}, y_{diff}) \sim \mathcal{U} \left[(x_{max} - x_{min}), \left(y_{\rho, diff} \pm \frac{w_{diff}}{2} \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

where $y_{\rho, diff}$ represents the center of the DI scattering region on both sides of the road whereas w_{diff} is the width of the DI scattering region. x_{min} and x_{max} represent the starting and ending points of the road, respectively. The number of DI scatterers is determined by $\eta \times (x_{max} - x_{min})$, where η represents DI scatterers density. The distribution of DI scatterers along the curved road follow the transitions of the outermost lanes as shown in Fig. 2.

B. Vehicle Type and Route

For our analysis, we considered three types of vehicles:

- Regular passenger car located in (L-1, L-2, RL-1, and RL-2).
- Medium-sized van located in (RL-0).
- Passenger bus located in (L-0).

The types and dimensions of the vehicles are given in Table 1. The Tx and Rx are located in the middle lanes (L-1, RL-1) as shown in Fig. 1. The vehicles are assigned distinct starting velocities. However, the velocities are not constant throughout the simulation. A difference of ± 4 m/s is introduced to represent a realistic traffic scenario.

The mobility is modeled in such a way that the Tx and two Dynamic Targets (DT) in lanes (L-0, L-2) are located at one end of the road. Similarly, the Rx and two DT in lanes (RL-0, RL-2) are located at the opposite end of the road. The vehicles approach each other and cross over at different time instants, determined by their initial positions and velocities. After crossing one another, the vehicles continue moving towards the end of the road. We have considered a simulation time (t_{sim}) of 25 s for our study. During the t_{sim} , we monitor the distance, delay, and Doppler characteristics of all the vehicles. Moreover, the Angle of Arrival (AoA) at DT from Tx, and the Angle of Departure (AoD) from DT towards Rx are also evaluated throughout the simulation.

It is important to point out that the position and velocity of vehicles remain unchanged in both setups. The only difference lies in the shape of the roads. In the straight road setup, variations occur only along the x -axis, while the y -axis remains constant. In contrast, the curved road setup exhibits changes in both the x -axis and y -axis.

C. Simulation Tools

For our simulation, we use three tools.

- For traffic generation on the road, we use Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO) [30], an open-source tool for simulating and analyzing traffic. SUMO is the most commonly used tool for generating realistic traffic traces. Its integration with other tools such as MATLAB and OMNeT++ makes it ideal for interdisciplinary research.
- For signal processing, we have adopted MATLAB because of its efficient built-in functions and matrix operations, and easy visualizations of signals in frequency and time domains. With MATLAB, different channel parameters and responses for Direct Link (DL), Indirect Link via Dynamic Targets (IDL-DT), and Indirect Link via Diffuse Scatterers (IDL-DI) are calculated. Moreover, received power, excess delay, Doppler shift, trajectory information, and detection capabilities are also evaluated with MATLAB.
- For simulating the bistatic TR of different vehicles at a frequency of 5.9 GHz, Altair FEKO is used. It supports several electromagnetic solvers, making it ideal for simulating complex electromagnetic interactions.

It is critical to point out that the tools used in our simulations do not necessarily represent the best tools available or indicate superior performance of selected tools over other similar tools. Our selection was based on personal preference, resource availability, and the specific requirements of our study.

III. BISTATIC RADAR CROSS SECTION OF VEHICLES

In wireless communication, not only the DL between Tx and Rx but also the scattering from the objects between the Tx and Rx is equally important for wireless channel modeling. Those scattering objects are generally modeled as omnidirectional scatterers with constant power and uniformly distributed phase shift over 0 to 2π [31], [32]. As a consequence, the geometry information of the scatterer, such as shape, size, and composed materials, and the wave information, such as the incidence angle, scattering angle, and polarization, are missing. For this reason, RCS from radar sensing has the mentioned properties, and therefore, it is proposed to apply in wireless channel estimation [33]. However, both wireless communication and radar sensing cases are under the assumption of far-field condition and narrow band.

Under the ISAC framework, we would like to propose the term "Reflectivity," instead of RCS, to represent the scattering behavior of the scattering objects. This "Reflectivity" encompasses geometry information, such as its shape, size, and material composition, and wave information, such as the aspect angles of incidence, scattering, and polarization. In addition, reflectivity is generalized as being dependent on distance and ultra-wideband. Consequently, the reflectivity model covers both near-field and far-field conditions, making it better suited for near-field channel estimation and near-field sensing. By ultra-wideband generalization, it is now possible to explore the reflection behavior in the time domain, such as extended target information.

In this study, the scenario of interest is a typical ISAC-enabled V2V scenario, where a transmitting vehicle Tx, a receiving vehicle Rx, and target vehicles DT¹ are present. The target vehicles are positioned between Tx and Rx. This Tx-Target-Rx constellation is known as a "bistatic" configuration in radar sensing. (If Tx and Rx are collocated, the system follows a "monostatic" configuration, which is not our focus in this study.)

In the bistatic configuration, the transmitted electromagnetic wave from Tx illuminates the target vehicle at the incident angle ϕ_{inc} ², and the target vehicle reflects the received power towards Rx at the scattering angle ϕ_{scat} ³. Since the scenario satisfies the far-field condition and we are considering a narrow-band case of wireless communication, the reflectivity of the target vehicles can still be modeled as its bistatic RCS of radar sensing perspective.

The reflecting/scattering link is modeled using the bistatic radar equation, and the DT can be modeled by their respective bistatic RCS values. The received power at the Rx for a bistatic radar can be described as follows:

$$P_{Rx,min} = \frac{P_{Tx} G_{Tx} G_{Rx} \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^3 (R_{Tx \rightarrow DT})^2 (R_{DT \rightarrow Rx})^2} \sigma_{bi}, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{Rx,min}$ is the minimum received power at Rx to detect the DT, P_{Tx} is the transmitted power, G_{Tx} and G_{Rx} are the gains of the transmitting and receiving antennas, λ is the wavelength, $R_{Tx \rightarrow DT}$ is the distance between Tx and DT, $R_{DT \rightarrow Rx}$ is the distance between the DT and Rx. σ_{bi} is the bistatic RCS value of DT, and it is the parameter of our interest.

The scalar bistatic RCS can be described by the following equation [34].

$$\sigma_{bi}(\phi_{inc}, \phi_{scat}) = \lim_{R_{Rx} \rightarrow \infty} 4\pi R_{Rx}^2 \frac{|E_s(\phi_{scat})|^2}{|E_i(\phi_{inc})|^2} \quad (3)$$

E_s is the scattered electric field and E_i is the incident electric field. The σ_{bi} of a DT depends on factors such as size,

¹Scattering vehicle and target vehicle refer to DT.

²The incident angle ϕ_{inc} at the scattering vehicles from Tx can be recognized as the AoA.

³The scattering angle ϕ_{scat} from the scattering vehicles to Rx can be recognized as the AoD.

These terms are used interchangeably throughout this paper.

shape, material composition, the incident and scattering wave aspects, the radar frequency, and the wave polarization.

TABLE 1. RCS Simulation Setup.

Vehicles	Type	Length (m)	Width (m)	Height (m)
	Passenger Car	4.9	1.9	1.5
	Van	6	2.0	2.0
	Bus	12	2.5	3.0
Frequency	5.9 GHz			
EM Software	FEKO 2021			
EM Solver	Physical Optic (PO-full ray-tracing)			
	Ray launching- Geometrical Optics (RL-GO)			
Material	Perfect electrical conductor (PEC)			
Azimuth Scan	$\phi_{inc} = 0 : 0.5 : 360^\circ$, $\phi_{scat} = 0 : 0.5 : 360^\circ$			
Simulated Parameter	Bistatic RCS (dBsm)			

A. Acquisition of bistatic RCS

In this study, the σ_{bi} of three different vehicles commonly found in daily traffic is simulated by Altair FEKO software at a frequency of 5.9 GHz. The simulation setup is described in Table 1.

These vehicle models, which differ significantly in their sizes and geometric shapes, are selected on purpose to observe how their scattering impacts the overall vehicular channel and target detection capability. To reduce simulation time and computational expense, we defined the materials of vehicles as Perfect Electric Conductor (PEC) and used asymptotic solvers, such as Physical Optics (PO) and RL-Geometric Optics (GO). In addition, the elevation level changes in the traffic are neglected, which means the road is assumed to be flat or no inclination. It allowed us to shorten the simulation time by neglecting the elevation angles. The incident angles ϕ_{inc} (AoA at the DT) are 0° to 360° with 0.5° angular step. For each ϕ_{inc} , there are the scattering angles ϕ_{scat} (AoD from the DT) of $0 : 0.5 : 360^\circ$.

The simulated bistatic RCS of the bus and its scattering behavior are illustrated in Fig. 3. The scattering behavior can generally be categorized as backscattering, specular scattering, forward scattering, and diffuse/non-specular⁴ scattering. When the strong scattering wave reflects in the direction of the incident wave, it is known as backscattering. It is also known as monostatic RCS, which is widely used in radar sensing. When the scattering wave reflects at the same angle value as the incident wave to the normal line perpendicular to the object's surface, the specular scattering/reflection occurs. This phenomenon is the same as light reflection. The number of specular scattering depends on the incident wave angles

⁴Low reflection non-specular scattering is diffuse scattering. However, it will be used as "non-specular" scattering in this work to avoid confusion with DI scatterers.

(a) Simulated bistatic RCS of bus for incidence wave at 30° (blue) and 90° (green).

(b) Simulated bistatic RCS of bus: Forward scattering.

(c) Simulated bistatic RCS of bus: Specular scatterings.

FIGURE 3. The simulated bistatic RCS of bus and its scattering behavior

and the geometry shape of the object. The forward scattering occurs when the bistatic angle between the scattering and incident wave is 180°. This scattering phenomenon is applied to sensing the stealth target; and is known as the forward scattering radar (FSR). These three scatterings are typically strong reflections, and their scattering directions can be predicted based on the incident wave angle and the object’s geometric structure. The weak scatterings/reflections into the other scattering angles are defined as non-specular scattering.

In general, these scattering behaviors and their scattering angles can be stated as follows:

- Backscattering: $\phi_{scat} = \phi_{inc}$,
- Forward scattering: $\phi_{scat} = 180^\circ + \phi_{inc}$.

Only if $\phi_{inc} \neq 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ, 270^\circ$ and 360° ,

- Specular scattering 1: $\phi_{scat} = 180^\circ - \phi_{inc} \rightarrow \phi_{inc} < 180^\circ$,
- Specular scattering 1: $\phi_{scat} = 540^\circ - \phi_{inc} \rightarrow \phi_{inc} > 180^\circ$,
- Specular sc

The rest are non-specular scattering components.

In Fig. 3a, the green plot is the simulated bistatic RCS for the incident wave at 90°. Since the incident wave is perpendicular to the flat surface of the bus, the strong backscattering is introduced in the direction of the incident wave. And the forward scattering is toward 270°, which is 90°+180°, and the rest is non-specular scattering. In Fig. 3a, the blue plot is the simulated bistatic RCS for the incident wave at 30°, which is not perpendicular to any flat surface of the bus. Therefore, the first specular scattering is introduced with the reflected angle 90°-30°= 60° to the normal at the side of the bus, which makes 150° in the polar plot. The second specular scattering is with the reflected angle 30° to the normal at the front of the bus, which makes 330° in the polar plot. In addition, the forward scattering is at 30°+180°= 210°. The simulated bistatic RCS for the incident wave at 90° and 30° are mapped into Fig. 3b and 3c, and the strong scatterings are labeled for all ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} cases.

The 3D models of the chosen vehicles, the simulated bistatic RCS, and the fitted Probability Distribution Function (pdf) with the Gaussian Mixture Model are illustrated in Fig. 4. These distribution models can serve as target fluctuation models in a more detailed analysis of target detection and radar performance.

In literature, the measured RCS and pdf model of various vehicles can be found [35]–[37]. However, these measurements and models are primarily based on different operating frequency bands, such as Ku and automotive radar frequency bands, and are obtained for monostatic configuration. Therefore, those models are not directly applicable to our study, which focuses on a bistatic configuration within the 5.9 GHz band. Given the current literature’s limitations, EM simulation is the most suitable approach for accurately modeling bistatic RCS within the 5.9 GHz band.

The derived distribution models may vary when the influence of traffic is taken into account as in [38]. Therefore, the later sections present how the aspect angles (or AoA, AoD) change according to the traffic flow and vehicle distribution, how these aspect angles influence the σ_{bi} and its pdf, and how this σ_{bi} variation affects the overall vehicular channel performance and target detection capability.

FIGURE 4. 3D Model of three different vehicles, simulated TR as bistatic RCS and their p.d.f with best-fit distributions.

B. Calculation of TR as bistatic RCS for Different Traffic Information

It is interesting to note that Fig. 4 presents the σ_{bi} value distribution for different vehicle models over all possible combinations of ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} . Nevertheless, only a limited range of these values is observed during the simulation. The selection of the σ_{bi} value of the DT depends on:

- position of Tx, Rx, and the DT,
- the lane in which the vehicle is located,
- the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} .

As the changes in the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} are not that abrupt and occur slowly over time, to accurately calculate the σ_{bi} value, the step size has been reduced from 0.5° to 0.01° through interpolation. In this way, we can calculate the σ_{bi} value for even the slightest change in the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} . The σ_{bi} can be calculated from the extensive $M \times N$ dataset of σ_{bi} values \mathcal{R} as shown in (4), where M and N correspond to the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} , respectively.

$$\mathcal{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{bi(1,1)} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \sigma_{bi(1,N)} \\ \sigma_{bi(2,1)} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \sigma_{bi(2,N)} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ \sigma_{bi(M-1,1)} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \sigma_{bi(M-1,N)} \\ \sigma_{bi(M,1)} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \sigma_{bi(M,N)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The entries $\sigma_{bi(m,n)}$ of the \mathcal{R} denote the σ_{bi} values corresponding to the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} values for a certain vehicle. For all the vehicles at a given time instant, ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} are determined, and the corresponding $\sigma_{bi(m,n)}$ value for the given pair is selected from the dataset. The values in the dataset are obtained by utilizing (3).

1) Variable TR Methodology

The ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} for a specific DT (k) and at a given instant of time (t_{inst}) is calculated as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{inc}(k, t_{inst}) &= \arctan \left(\frac{y(k, t_{inst}) - y(Tx, t_{inst})}{x(k, t_{inst}) - x(Tx, t_{inst})} \right), \\ \phi_{scat}(k, t_{inst}) &= \arctan \left(\frac{y(k, t_{inst}) - y(Rx, t_{inst})}{x(k, t_{inst}) - x(Rx, t_{inst})} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

As stated earlier, we encounter different ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} values for different vehicles, we have a different distribution of σ_{bi} values as compared to the ones shown in Fig. 4. For a specific pair of ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} , we calculate the σ_{bi} value from \mathcal{R} . As the position of the Tx, Rx, and DT change over time, so does the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} which leads to time-varying TR for DT ⁵.

⁵In this study, the terms variable TR and dynamic RCS are used interchangeably.

2) Constant TR Methodology

We have varying distributions of σ_{bi} for different vehicles. The statistical characteristics (mean, median, and standard deviation (Std.)) of the σ_{bi} distributions are different from each other as given in Table 2. For a specific vehicle, the mean of the σ_{bi} is calculated and is utilized in the constant TR model⁶. The adopted constant RCS value is assumed to be the same throughout the simulation.

TABLE 2. Variable TR Modeling Statistics.

Vehicle	Straight Road Section			Curved Road Section		
	Mean	Median	Std.	Mean	Median	Std.
Bus	20.78	22.53	6.99	14.87	11.02	8.97
PC1	15.15	16.83	7.36	9.05	7.98	6.43
Van	9.49	7.51	9.99	8.17	7.41	6.57
PC2	11.97	9.46	9.81	9.62	8.38	6.75

IV. INTEGRATION OF DYNAMIC RCS INTO ISAC-ENABLED V2V CHANNEL MODEL

A. System Model

We consider a bistatic ISAC-enabled V2V system deployed across diverse geometrical layouts, where vehicles equipped with ISAC capabilities can simultaneously communicate and sense their surrounding environment. A bistatic configuration is adopted in our study due to its superior spatial diversity, which minimizes blind spots and enhances target detection—particularly in high-mobility and complex vehicular scenarios. Unlike monostatic sensing, which requires full-duplex operation and advanced self-interference cancellation techniques that are not widely supported in current V2V communication standards (5G-NR, C-V2X), the bistatic setup operates in a half-duplex mode, eliminating self-interference challenges. Moreover, the bistatic setup is well-suited for distributed deployments, making it an ideal candidate for cooperative vehicular networks.

In this system, vehicles exchange communication data via the DL while leveraging reflected signals from DTs and DI scatterers for environmental sensing. The system operates in half-duplex mode, where a Tx sends data packets to Rx, both located at different locations. At the Rx, three types of signals are received (DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI scatterers). By processing these reflected signals, the Rx not only decodes communication data but also functions as a bistatic radar, extracting key radar parameters such as the range and relative velocity of nearby vehicles from the transmitted signals. We have considered three major contributors to the overall channel response in our study which are given below:

1) Direct Link (DL)

⁶In this study, the terms constant TR and constant RCS are used interchangeably.

2) Indirect Link via DT (IDL-DT)

3) Indirect Link via DI scatterers (IDL-DI)

In this study, we have adopted the extended ISAC-enabled V2V channel model presented in [28], which is inspired by the V2V communication framework originally developed in [14]. The latter serves as a foundational model, designed specifically for V2V communication, which is extended to incorporate additional target sensing capabilities. However, a constant RCS value of 10 dBsm is assumed for all the DT in [28] without taking into consideration the orientation of Tx, Rx, and DT. Moreover, all vehicles are assumed to have the same type and dimensions.

These assumptions are unlikely to hold in real-life scenarios due to the highly dynamic nature of the vehicular environments. Factors such as different vehicle models, dimensions, and multipath effects can substantially influence the actual value of RCS and propagation channel characteristics.

In this study, we have adopted an omnidirectional antenna pattern to isolate and analyze the impact of dynamic RCS on channel magnitude and target detection capability. This ensures that the variations in detection performance are exclusively attributed to RCS variations, without any additional influences from antenna directivity or beam-forming effects.

To model the links between vehicles and generate channel responses, we have used a simplified single reflection-based Ray Tracing (RT) approach. The Channel Impulse Response (CIR) can be represented as:

$$h(t, \tau) = \sum_s G_{Tx} G_{Rx} \alpha_s e^{j2\pi f_{D,s} t} \delta(\tau - \tau_s), \quad (6)$$

where τ_s and $f_{D,s}$ represent the excess delay and Doppler shift of path s , respectively. $G_{Tx/Rx}$ represents the constant amplitude gain of the transmitting and receiving antennas. The amplitude of the path s is represented by α_s . As stated earlier, at the Rx, the signal is received from the DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI scatterers. The propagation delay of different paths is different from one another, depending upon the position of Tx, Rx, and DT/ DI scatterer. The maximum excess delay of the Multipath Components (MPCs) is less than 4 ms, whereas the sampling interval is 10 ms. It is assumed in our setup that all MPCs arrive within a single sampling period, ensuring that the channel remains consistent within each sample but may evolve over consecutive samples due to the mobility of Tx, Rx, and DT.

The performance of the ISAC-enabled V2V system, in our study, is evaluated under certain assumptions which are:

- The DL from Tx to the Rx is always available, ensuring a continuous data transmission.
- There are no blockages in the links between Tx and DT, as well as between the DT and Rx. Only a single reflection is considered in the setup.
- The links for the DI scatterers are considered only with Tx and Rx on the road, without any interference from moving DT.

- The channel is assumed to remain invariant between two consecutive sampling instances, with variations considered only when a new sample is drawn i.e., after 10 ms.
- The elevation level changes in the geometrical layouts are neglected, which means the road is assumed to be flat. It allowed us to shorten the simulation time by ignoring the elevation angles in the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} .

B. Direct Link (DL)

The DL component defines the link between Tx and Rx when no vehicles or obstacles are blocking the path. The DL channel response is given by:

$$h_{DL}(t, \tau) = \alpha_{DL}(t) e^{j2\pi f_{D,DL} t} \delta(\tau - \tau_{DL}), \quad (7)$$

where $f_{D,DL}$ and τ_{DL} represent the Doppler shift and propagation delay for the DL component, respectively. The amplitude α_{DL} is given by [14], [29]:

$$\alpha_{DL}(t) = P_{0,DL}^{1/2} \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}} \right)^{n_{DL}/2}, \quad (8)$$

where $P_{0,DL}$ is the reference power for the DL component at $d_{ref} = 1$ m, n_{DL} represents the path-loss exponent and $d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}$ is the distance between Tx and Rx. The delay and Doppler shift for the DL component is calculated as:

$$\tau_{DL} = \frac{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}}{c}, \quad (9)$$

$$f_{D,DL} = \left(\frac{(\mathbf{v}_{Tx} - \mathbf{v}_{Rx})^T \odot (\mathbf{p}_{Tx} - \mathbf{p}_{Rx})}{d_{Tx \rightarrow Rx}} \right) \times \frac{f_c}{c} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{v}_{Tx} , \mathbf{v}_{Rx} , f_c , and c represent Tx velocity, Rx velocity, carrier frequency, and speed of light, respectively. \mathbf{p}_{Tx} and \mathbf{p}_{Rx} are the position vectors of Tx and Rx, respectively.

C. Indirect Link via Dynamic Targets (IDL-DT)

IDL-DT components refer to the Indirect Link (IDL), which result from other moving vehicles on the road, i.e., Tx \rightarrow $k \rightarrow$ Rx (where k denotes the k^{th} DT). The IDL-DT channel response can be mathematically expressed as:

$$h_{DT}(t, \tau) = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k(t) e^{j2\pi f_{D,k} t} \delta(\tau - \tau_k), \quad (11)$$

where $f_{D,k}$ and τ_k represent the Doppler shift and propagation delay for the k^{th} DT. K is the total number of DT in our scenario. The amplitude for the k^{th} DT is given as:

$$\alpha_k(t) = P_{0,k}^{1/2} \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow k}} \right)^{n_k/2} \left(\frac{\sigma_{bi,k}(t)}{4\pi(d_{k \rightarrow Rx})^{n_k}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

where $P_{0,k}$ is the reference power for the DT component, n_k is the path-loss exponent. $d_{Tx \rightarrow k}$ and $d_{k \rightarrow Rx}$ represent the distance from Tx to k^{th} DT, and from k^{th} DT to Rx, respectively. $\sigma_{bi,k}$ denotes the RCS value of the k^{th} DT which is obtained utilizing (4). The delay and Doppler shift for k^{th} DT is given as:

$$\tau_k = \frac{(d_{Tx \rightarrow k} + d_{k \rightarrow Rx})}{c}, \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{D,Tx \rightarrow k} &= - \left[\frac{(\mathbf{v}_k - \mathbf{v}_{Tx})^T \odot (\mathbf{p}_k - \mathbf{p}_{Tx})}{d_{Tx \rightarrow k}} \right] \times \frac{f_c}{c}, \\ f_{D,k \rightarrow Rx} &= - \left[\frac{(\mathbf{v}_{Rx} - \mathbf{v}_k)^T \odot (\mathbf{p}_k - \mathbf{p}_{Rx})}{d_{k \rightarrow Rx}} \right] \times \frac{f_c}{c}, \\ f_{D,k} &= f_{D,Tx \rightarrow k} + f_{D,k \rightarrow Rx}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{p}_k and \mathbf{v}_k denotes the position vector and velocity of the k^{th} DT. Doppler shift of the path $s_{1,Tx \rightarrow k}$ and $s_{2,k \rightarrow Rx}$ is represented by $f_{D,Tx \rightarrow k}$ and $f_{D,k \rightarrow Rx}$, respectively. The bistatic Doppler shift is represented by $f_{D,k}$.

D. Indirect Link via Diffuse Scatterers (IDL-DI)

The DI scatterers represent the point scatterers or vegetation on both sides of the road. The channel response for DI scatterers can be mathematically expressed as:

$$h_{diff}(t, \tau) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q(t) e^{j2\pi f_{D,q} t} \delta(\tau - \tau_q), \quad (15)$$

where $f_{D,q}$ and τ_q represent the Doppler shift and propagation delay for the q^{th} DI scatterer. Q is the total number of DI scatterers in our scenario. The amplitude of DI scatterer is modeled according to the classical Geometry-based Stochastic Channel Model (GBSCM) approach and is represented as [14]:

$$\alpha_q(t) = (P_{0,q})^{1/2} c_q \left(\frac{d_{ref}}{d_{Tx \rightarrow q} \times d_{q \rightarrow Rx}} \right)^{n_q/2}, \quad (16)$$

where $P_{0,q}$ represent the normalized reference power for q^{th} DI scatterer and n_q represents path-loss exponent. As the number of DI scatterers is quite large, to divide the power among them equally, we divide the reference power $P_{0,Q}$ by the total number of DI scatterers Q to get normalized power $P_{0,q}$. $d_{Tx \rightarrow q}$ and $d_{q \rightarrow Rx}$ represent the distance from Tx to the q^{th} DI scatterer, and from q^{th} DI scatterer to Rx, respectively. c_q denotes a zero-mean complex Gaussian random variable with unit variance whose real and imaginary parts are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d). c_q is represented as $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$. The delay for DI scatterers can be calculated similarly to the DT components given in (13). The Doppler shift for DI scatterers can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{D,Tx \rightarrow q} &= - \left[\frac{(0 - \mathbf{v}_{Tx})^T \odot (\mathbf{p}_q - \mathbf{p}_{Tx})}{d_{Tx \rightarrow q}} \right] \times \frac{f_c}{c}, \\ f_{D,q \rightarrow Rx} &= - \left[\frac{(\mathbf{v}_{Rx} - 0)^T \odot (\mathbf{p}_q - \mathbf{p}_{Rx})}{d_{q \rightarrow Rx}} \right] \times \frac{f_c}{c}, \\ f_{D,q} &= f_{D,Tx \rightarrow q} + f_{D,q \rightarrow Rx}, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{p}_q is the position vector of the q^{th} DI scatterer. As DI scatterers are assumed stationary in our scenario, the velocity component is always 0. Doppler shift of the path $s_{1,Tx \rightarrow q}$ and $s_{2,q \rightarrow Rx}$ represented by $f_{D,Tx \rightarrow q}$ and $f_{D,q \rightarrow Rx}$, respectively. The bistatic Doppler shift is represented by $f_{D,q}$.

E. Overall Channel Response

The overall channel response is derived by adding the contributions from the individual channel responses (i.e., DL component, DT components, and DI components), and is given as:

$$h(t, \tau) = h_{DL}(t, \tau) + h_{DT}(t, \tau) + h_{diff}(t, \tau). \quad (18)$$

F. Radar Processing for Target Detection

In our study, the radar signal processing occurs at the Rx in a bi-static radar configuration. The signal processing for target detection is performed using classical radar sensing. In our scenario, it is assumed that the Rx has the perfect knowledge of the transmitted signal, and is perfectly synchronized with the Tx. Inspired by [39], the received signal at the Rx is passed through a radar signal processing chain after the Cyclic Prefix (CP) removal and the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) operation. At first, the transmitted data symbols are removed from the received signal by taking the element-wise division with the transmitted signal to obtain the transfer function \mathbf{H} of the overall CIR $h(t)$. The transfer function matrix \mathbf{H} is then weighted by a 2D Hann window for delay-Doppler sidelobes reduction, followed by the 2D-Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) operation to transform \mathbf{H} in the delay-Doppler domain for parameter estimation. This operation is performed by computing the periodogram as follows

$$\mathcal{P}(n, m) = \left| \sum_{l=0}^{N_p-1} \left(\sum_{q=0}^{M_p-1} \mathbf{H}_{l,q} e^{-j2\pi \frac{qm}{M_p}} \right) e^{j2\pi \frac{ln}{N_p}} \right|^2. \quad (19)$$

The periodogram involves performing N_p -DFT of length M_p and M_p -Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform (IDFT) of length N_p on the channel transfer function matrix \mathbf{H} , where N_p and M_p represent the dimensions of the periodogram. The periodogram in (19) produces the delay-Doppler map in which the peaks represent the potential targets in the scenario. The peaks are identified based on a hypothesis test: whether a peak corresponds to a target echo (H_1) or is due to noise (H_0). This hypothesis test uses a threshold, determined from the estimated noise power, to achieve a desired false alarm rate. In this work, we applied the Cell-Averaging Constant False Alarm Rate (CA-CFAR) algorithm, which adaptively calculates the threshold for each cell by averaging the noise power in neighboring cells. The delay and Doppler shift for K DTs are then identified as the locations of K largest peaks in the periodogram under the H_1 hypothesis [40], as shown below:

$$(\hat{n}_k, \hat{m}_k) = \underset{n, m}{\operatorname{argmax}} \{ \mathcal{P}(n, m) \}, \quad k = 1, \dots, K. \quad (20)$$

Moreover, the range and relative velocity of the k^{th} DT, corresponding to the estimated delay and Doppler shift, is calculated as:

$$\hat{r}_k = \frac{\hat{n}_k c}{N_p \Delta f}, \quad \hat{v}_k = \frac{\hat{m}_k c}{f_c M_p T_s}, \quad (21)$$

where Δf and T_s represent the subcarrier spacing and OFDM symbol duration, respectively.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the simulation results of constant and variable TR integrated setups for the aforementioned geometrical road layouts at $f_c = 5.9$ GHz. The analysis will focus on how constant and variable TR integrated ISAC-enabled V2V setups impact channel magnitude and target detection accuracy. We have considered a constant transmitted power (P_{Tx}) of 23 dBm for both traffic scenarios. For Tx and Rx, a constant 1.5 dB of amplitude gain $G_{Tx/Rx}$ is considered, which is equivalent to a power gain of 3 dB.

The velocities and initial positions of the vehicles, along with other simulation parameters, are provided in Table 3.

TABLE 3. Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value		
Frequency	5.9 GHz		
Bandwidth	50 MHz		
Subcarrier Spacing	30 kHz		
Transmitted Power	23 dBm		
Vehicles' Position (x, y) and Speed (m/s)	L-0	(0, 2.5)	17 ± 4
	L-1	(150, 6.25)	23 ± 4
	L-2	(20, 11.75)	27 ± 4
	RL-0	(950, 24.75)	21 ± 4
	RL-1	(700, 20.25)	25 ± 4
	RL-2	(925, 15.75)	30 ± 4
Simulation Time	24.99 s		
Sample Time	10 ms		
Reference Power ($P_{0,X}$) and PL Exponents (n_X) [14], [28], [29]	DL	-17 dB	1.8
	IDL-DT	-22 dB	2.0
	IDL-DI	90 dB	5.4
Number of DT	4		
Range Resolution	6 m		
Velocity Resolution	2 m/s		
DI Scatterers Density (η)	1 m^{-2}		

One of the primary objectives of an ISAC-enabled V2V system is to be able to detect and distinguish a TOI from the unwanted clutter. To successfully detect and distinguish TOI from clutter, the back-scattered signal from the TOI should be sufficiently higher than the strongest clutter (DI scatterer) for accurate identification. The performance of an ISAC-enabled V2V system can be evaluated with the analysis of channel magnitudes for different components such as DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI scatterers. The channel magnitude variations influence critical sensing performance indicators such as target detection accuracy and localization precision. Higher channel magnitudes indicate stronger received signals, which in turn correspond to enhanced performance of communication and radar sensing. The variations due to the IDL-DI scattering components may introduce instabilities that can impact target detection reliability, particularly in a clutter-rich environment.

It is important to emphasize that this study does not assess communication performance of the ISAC-enabled V2V system. Instead, the focus is on radar sensing performance under constant and variable TR setups. In this study, we suppose an ideal communication link such as DL is always available, ensuring uninterrupted data transmission. Our primary interest lies in understanding the impact of constant and variable TR on radar sensing performance within an ISAC framework. However, as previously mentioned, a higher channel magnitude generally enhances both communication and sensing performance, reinforcing the dual benefits of ISAC systems.

Moreover, we have performed target detection throughout the simulation. However, we have chosen specific time instances for which the target detection snapshots are displayed. It is critical to indicate that the selected time instants do not offer optimal performance, but rather exhibit the behavior at specific time instances, without implying that these represent the points of best performance.

A. Straight Road Section

Dynamic RCS values' distribution depends on the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} . As the vehicles move, their position and associated angles change. As a result, we get time-varying RCS values for the straight road section as shown in Fig. 5. Along with the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} , the RCS values depend on the shape and dimensions of DT as well. The RCS characteristics of the front of the DT can be significantly different from the back of the DT, depending upon its shape and dimensions.

As the straight road section has no sharp turns, it presents a straightforward case. The bus in L-0 shows higher RCS values because of its size and dimensions. The PC1 in L-2 also has higher values for the first half of the simulation resulting from ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} combination. The van in RL-0 has higher RCS values after the cross-over as the incident ray from Tx is reflected from the back of the van. PC2 in RL-2 exhibits a similar behavior. The statistical properties including mean, median, and standard deviation of the RCS

FIGURE 5. Variation of RCS values over time.

for all the vehicles are given in Fig. 6. Based on the above factors, the distribution and statistical properties of RCS differ for each vehicle, as indicated in Fig. 6.

1) Channel Magnitude of DT

The channel magnitude of the constant and dynamic RCS integrated ISAC-enabled V2V channel models are shown in Fig. 7. The constant RCS integrated model results in smooth curves for channel magnitude as evident from Fig. 7a. The channel magnitude is modeled in such a way that it is distance-dependent. At the start of the simulation, the distance from Tx to the Rx (d_{DL}) and the bistatic distance of DT (d_{DT}) is maximum. As a result, the corresponding channel magnitude is low at the start of the simulation. The channel magnitude increases as the vehicles approach the crossing point and d_{DL} and d_{DT} decrease. The vehicles cross each other at different time instants, depending upon their initial position and velocity. After the crossover, the d_{DL} and d_{DT} increase again resulting in low channel magnitude towards the end of the simulation. Vehicles positioned in the inner lanes (L-2, RL-2) exhibit a higher channel magnitude than those in lanes L-0 and RL-0, as illustrated in Fig. 7a. This happens because the d_{DT} of vehicles located on inner lanes is smaller compared to the vehicles on outer lanes, leading to higher channel magnitude.

Similarly, the channel magnitudes resulting from the dynamic RCS integrated model are shown in Fig. 7b. The variations resulting from dynamic RCS can be seen in the respective channel magnitudes of the vehicles. At every time instant, we have a different RCS value depending upon the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} of the DT. We calculate the RCS value for all the vehicles according to (4). In dynamic RCS setup, the vehicles located at the inner lanes also result in higher channel magnitude compared to vehicles in the outer lanes. However, this variation in the channel magnitude is higher compared to the constant RCS integrated model.

2) DL, DI, and joint DT Channel Magnitude

The channel magnitude of all the DT is summed to form a joint DT channel magnitude. For a constant RCS integrated model, the channel magnitude for DL, joint DT, and DI scatterers is given in Fig. 8a. The DL results in the highest channel magnitude. This stems from the fact that the distance of the DL is always shorter than the IDL-DT and IDL-DI. The channel magnitude for the joint DT is higher than DI scatterers' channel magnitude except during $10\text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 13\text{ s}$. As the channel magnitude is distance-dependent, the distance of some of the DI scatterers is less as compared to DT, thus resulting in higher channel magnitude. The joint DT channel magnitude exhibits significant variations due to differing d_{DT} . Initially, the d_{DT} being large, we see less fluctuation in the channel magnitude. However, as these distances decrease, more functions can be observed in the

FIGURE 6. RCS values distribution for straight road section.

second half of the simulation. The distance between Tx and PC1 ($d_{Tx \rightarrow PC1}$) and Rx and PC2 ($d_{Rx \rightarrow PC2}$) is higher at the start of the simulation. However, as the vehicles (PC1, PC2) move at a higher speed as compared to Tx and Rx, they catch up with them, and the respective distances ($d_{Tx \rightarrow PC1}$, $d_{Rx \rightarrow PC2}$) decrease towards the end. As a result, we see more variation towards the end of the simulation.

In a similar manner, the channel magnitudes for DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI for dynamic RCS integrated model are shown in Fig. 8b. The difference occurs only in the channel magnitude of joint DT which now has more peaks resulting from the peak values of dynamic RCS. As for the dynamic RCS setup, we have a different RCS value at each time instant, we can observe the fluctuations in the joint channel magnitude of DT. The peak of the joint DT channel magnitude is recorded at $t_{sim} = 17.5$ s. This peak results from the highest RCS value of the DT in RL-2. Moreover, the difference between joint DT and DI scatterers' channel magnitude is also smaller during $10 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 12 \text{ s}$ as compared to the constant RCS integrated model.

3) Overall Channel Magnitude and Time-Dependent Variations in CIR

The overall channel magnitude results from adding all the components, i.e., DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI as shown in (18). The overall channel magnitude for the constant RCS integrated model is shown in Fig. 9a. As DL is the strongest component throughout the simulation, it has the most influence on the overall channel magnitude. There is little to no variation in the overall channel magnitude of the constant RCS integrated model. These small variations in the overall channel magnitude come from the DT.

Similarly, the overall channel magnitude for the dynamic RCS integrated model is given in Fig. 9b. In the dynamic RCS setup, the DL remains the strongest component, followed by the DT and DI scatterers, respectively. As we can see in Fig. 5, frequent variations in RCS values are observed during the period $14.5 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 18 \text{ s}$. During this period, vehicles cross one another resulting in large changes in ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} . Significant variations in overall channel magnitude for the dynamic RCS integrated model are recorded for the interval $16 \text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 19 \text{ s}$. These variations can help us differentiate a dynamic RCS setup from a constant RCS setup. Moreover, with the help of these

(a) Constant RCS integrated model

(b) Dynamic RCS integrated model

FIGURE 7. Channel magnitude of DT.

(a) Constant RCS integrated model

(b) Dynamic RCS integrated model

FIGURE 8. Channel magnitude of DL, joint DT, and DI component.

variations, the DT can be easily detected, thus resulting in accurate target detection.

Similarly, the CIR time-dependent variations for the constant and dynamic RCS integrated setups are shown in Fig. 10. The primary difference between these models lies in the power levels. However, these differences are not easily distinguishable from Fig. 10a and 10b. All the components such as DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI scatterers are visible in Fig. 10. At the beginning of the simulation, the vehicles are at their extreme positions, resulting in higher propagation delays. As the vehicles move toward the crossover point, the propagation delay for both the DL and IDL gradually decreases. Once they pass the crossover point, the vehicles move in opposite directions, causing the propagation delay to increase again.

The DL from the Tx results in the highest channel magnitude and shortest propagation delay compared to the IDL. For most of the simulation, the channel magnitude of DT in different lanes is higher and their propagation delay is lower than DI scatterers. However, there are time durations during which the propagation delay of closely located DI

scatterers is lower than the DT. Similarly, in such cases, the channel magnitude of these DI scatterers surpasses that of the DT. These observations in the CIR for constant and variable RCS integrated models align with the findings presented in Fig. 8, reinforcing that the DL consistently results in the highest channel magnitude, followed by joint DT and DI scatterers.

4) Target Detection in Constant and Dynamic RCS Integrated Models

The snapshots of target detection for constant and dynamic RCS integrated models at different time instants are shown in Fig. 11. The snapshots indicate the presence of all components, i.e., DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI. The components can be distinguished from one another. The DL and IDL-DT are labeled with a square block in Fig. 11. The rest indicates the DI scattering components, which are treated as clutter in the scenario. The red and black ellipses highlight the different power levels of DT for constant and dynamic RCS setups. The red ellipse indicates a higher power level whereas the

FIGURE 9. Overall channel magnitude.

FIGURE 10. CIR time-dependent variations.

black ellipse indicates a lower power level for a particular DT at the same time instant. The dynamic RCS value varies based on the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} at any given time. There are moments when the dynamic RCS value falls below the mean RCS value, reflecting a more realistic scenario. In contrast, a constant RCS setup does not represent realistic behavior as the orientation of Tx, Rx, and DT has no impact on the constant value of RCS.

The target detection results of dynamic and constant RCS integrated models are compared at $t_{sim} = 1.47$ s in Fig. 11a and 11d, respectively. It can be seen that the DL from Tx results in the highest power and can be very easily distinguished from the remaining DT and clutter in the scenario. The DT in L-0 (bus) and L-2 (PC1) for a dynamic RCS integrated model have relatively higher power levels than the constant RCS integrated model. This is due to the higher values of RCS for the bus and PC1. The dynamic value of RCS for bus and PC1 at $t_{sim} = 1.47$ s is 28.33 dBsm and 23.31 dBsm, respectively. In contrast, the constant RCS value throughout the simulation for the bus and PC1 is 20.78 dBsm and 15.15 dBsm, respectively. The power levels

of the DT in the periodogram depend on the respective RCS values. For DT in RL-2 (PC2), the power level in the constant RCS model is higher than the dynamic RCS model. At the given time instant, the dynamic RCS for PC2 is 3.09 dBsm, which is lower than the constant RCS value i.e., 11.97 dBsm. As a result, for PC2, the dynamic RCS setup leads to a lower power level than the constant RCS setup.

Similarly, the target detection snapshots at $t_{sim} = 13.29$ s for constant and dynamic RCS integrated models are given in Fig. 11b and 11e, respectively. The dynamic RCS integrated model for PC1 results in a higher power level than the constant RCS integrated model. An RCS value of 18.10 dBsm is obtained whereas the constant RCS value is 15.15 dBsm. This results in higher power levels for PC1. On the other hand, the constant RCS model results in relatively higher power levels for the remaining DT such as bus, van, and PC2. However, the difference in power levels is not significant. The weaker power levels correspond to the clutter, i.e., DI scattering components. As DI scatterers are stationary, but Tx and Rx are in motion, different Doppler shift values are observed for DI scatterers based on their position and

FIGURE 11. Target detection with: constant RCS integrated model ((a), (b), (c)), dynamic RCS integrated model ((d), (e), (f)).

distance relative to Tx and Rx. This phenomenon is evident in Fig. 11b and 11e, where the closely located DI scatterers and their corresponding Doppler shift values are depicted. Similarly, the snapshots of target detection for constant and dynamic RCS integrated models at $t_{sim} = 14.62$ s are given in Fig. 11c and 11f, respectively. As a result of the trajectory, the DT in L-2 and RL-2 merge, appearing as a single target. The DT in RL-0 (van) has the highest power for the dynamic RCS integrated model which results from the high dynamic RCS value of 31.60 dBsm. In contrast, the van’s constant RCS value is 9.45 dBsm. The dynamic RCS values of the remaining DT are lower than the constant RCS value. As a result, the power levels of the remaining DT are higher in the constant RCS integrated model compared to the dynamic RCS integrated model. Thus, at certain moments, the dynamic RCS values can fall below the mean RCS value, leading to lower power levels.

B. Curved Road Section

The curved road section introduces greater variation in RCS values distribution as vehicles navigate along the curved path. These variations are more profound compared to those seen in the straight road section where vehicles follow a straight path. This results from the fact that the curved path

FIGURE 12. Variation of RCS values over time.

causes more frequent changes in ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} , resulting in more widely distributed RCS values. As there are different types of vehicles in different lanes, the distribution of RCS values is different for each vehicle as shown in Fig. 13. The bus in L-0 results in the highest value of RCS i.e. 52.50 dBsm.

The curves in the path cause abrupt changes in ϕ_{inc} and

FIGURE 13. RCS values distribution for curved road section.

ϕ_{scat} leading to sharp peaks in RCS values distribution as illustrated in Fig. 12. These peaks occur more frequently on the curved path compared to the straight road section. In the straight road section, the peaks are primarily observed when vehicles pass each other as this alignment can result in higher RCS values. However, for the curved path, the changes in ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} are quite frequent, thus resulting in more frequent peaks.

1) Channel Magnitude of DT

The channel magnitude of the DT for the constant RCS integrated model is given in Fig. 14a. In the constant RCS integrated model, the mean value of the RCS for each vehicle is used. It remains constant throughout the simulation and results in smooth curves. The channel magnitude is distance-dependent. At the start of the simulation, lowest values for channel magnitude are recorded for DT due to their maximum initial distance d_{DT} . As the vehicles approach each other, the distance between them decreases toward the center of the path until the crossover point for each vehicle is reached. As a result of this decreasing distance, the respective channel magnitude of DT is increased. The

distance begins to increase once the crossover point is crossed, leading to a decrease in the channel magnitude towards the end of the simulation. Since vehicles in different lanes have varying starting positions and velocities, the peaks of the channel magnitude curves for each DT occur at different time instants as shown in Fig. 14a.

Similarly, the channel magnitudes for the dynamic RCS integrated model are given in Fig. 14b. The variations in the RCS value in the dynamic RCS integrated model are depicted in the channel magnitude. The channel magnitude curves for the DT show frequent variations depending on the respective RCS values. As the vehicles pass through the curved path, the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} undergo frequent changes, resulting in the variation of the DT channel magnitude. As the DT such as PC1 and PC2 are positioned on the inner lanes, their respective d_{DT} is lower than the vehicles (bus, van) in the outer lanes. As a result, higher channel magnitude is observed for PC1 and PC2 compared to the bus and van. For the bus in L-0 and van in RL-0, high values of RCS are recorded for the second half of the simulation. As a result, the channel magnitudes of the bus and van achieve higher values in the second half of the simulation. The channel magnitude curves indicate frequent variations

(a) Constant RCS integrated model

(b) Dynamic RCS integrated model

FIGURE 14. Channel magnitude of DT.

(a) Constant RCS integrated model

(b) Dynamic RCS integrated model

FIGURE 15. Channel magnitude of DL, joint DT, and DI component.

in the channel magnitude for the dynamic RCS integrated model for the curved path. The variations recorded for the curved path are much higher compared to the straight road section. These variations are caused by the nature of the path, which leads to frequent changes in the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} , resulting in fluctuating RCS values.

2) DL, DI and joint DT Channel Magnitude

The channel magnitudes of DL, IDL-DI, and joint DT for constant RCS integrated model are given in Fig. 15a. The DL results in the highest channel magnitude throughout the simulation. The joint DT channel magnitude is higher as compared to the DI scatterers channel magnitude throughout the simulation except for the region between $10\text{ s} \leq t_{sim} \leq 15\text{ s}$. The distance of some of the DI scatterers is lower than the DT, which results in a higher channel magnitude compared to the joint DT. The variations in the joint DT channel magnitude result from contributions from all the DT. Similarly, the channel magnitude of DL, IDL-DI, and joint DT for the dynamic RCS integrated model are shown in Fig.

15b. There is no change in the channel magnitude of DL and IDL-DI, as the variations due to the dynamic RCS are only visible in the joint DT channel magnitude. The joint DT channel magnitude for the dynamic RCS integrated model is relatively higher and has more frequent variations compared to the constant RCS integrated model. This stems from the fact that the vehicles in different lanes experience dynamic changes in channel magnitude, driven by varying RCS values at different time instants. As a result, we see varying peaks in the joint DT channel magnitude throughout the simulation. These variations, depending upon the respective RCS values, can go as high as DL channel magnitude.

3) Overall Channel Magnitude

The overall channel magnitude results from the summation of the contributions from all the components. The overall channel magnitude for the constant RCS integrated model is shown in Fig. 16a. We can see a smooth curve channel magnitude response with minimal to no variations. The DL contributes most to the overall channel magnitude. As a

FIGURE 16. Overall channel magnitude.

FIGURE 17. CIR time-dependent variations.

result, the shape of the overall channel magnitude curve closely follows the DL channel magnitude curve. The small variations in the overall channel magnitude come from the DT and DI scatterers.

On the other hand, the overall channel magnitude for the dynamic RCS integrated model is exhibited in Fig. 16b. We can see very sharp variations in the second half of the simulation. In the first half of the simulation, the joint DT channel magnitude has little variation as shown in Fig. 16b. Higher fluctuations are observed in the second half of the simulation due to rapidly changing RCS values of the DT. The highest dynamic RCS values are also recorded for the second half of the simulation. As a result, the overall channel magnitude exhibits numerous fluctuations in the latter half of the simulation. These sharp fluctuations distinctly differentiate the dynamic RCS integrated model from the constant RCS integrated model.

The CIR variations for the curved road setup are displayed in Fig. 17. Similar to the straight-road setup, all components (DL, IDL-DT, and IDL-DI scatterers) can be easily observed

in Fig. 17. The time-dependent variations in the CIR for the constant RCS integrated model are displayed in Fig. 17a, while the variations for the dynamic RCS integrated setup are depicted in Fig. 17b. The important distinction between these two setups lies in the sharp variations of the channel magnitude values as the vehicles pass through the curved path. However, this distinction is difficult to discern from Fig. 17a and Fig. 17b.

For the curved path, the DL results in the shortest propagation delay and the highest channel magnitude. Throughout most of the simulation, DT located in different lanes tends to have higher channel magnitudes and lower propagation delays compared to DI scatterers. However, there are time instants at which the relative distance of the closely placed DI scatterers from Tx and Rx is lower than the DT. As a result, the propagation delay is shorter and the channel magnitude is higher. These observations align with the results presented in Fig. 16, supporting that the DL results in the highest channel magnitude throughout the simulation, followed by the joint DT and DI scatterers.

FIGURE 18. Target detection with: constant RCS integrated model ((a), (b), (c)), dynamic RCS integrated model ((d), (e), (f)).

4) Target Detection in Constant and Dynamic RCS Models

The target detection snapshots at specific time instants for constant and dynamic RCS integrated models are shown in Fig. 18. The snapshots indicate that the distance-velocity plots can distinctly identify all the components. The DL from Tx always results in the highest component, followed by DT and DI scatterers. The different components can be identified from the power levels in the distance-velocity plots. For the curved road section, the DL and IDL-DT are represented by square blocks, while the remaining elements depict clutter in the scenario. The red and black ellipses highlight the respective power levels of the DT in both setups, with the red ellipse indicating a higher power level and the black ellipse representing a lower power level for a specific DT at the same time instant.

A comparison of target detection at $t_{sim} = 3.36$ s for constant and dynamic RCS integrated models is given in Fig. 18a and 18d, respectively. The power level of the DT in L-2 (PC1) is relatively higher in the dynamic RCS integrated model compared to the constant RCS integrated model. The dynamic RCS integrated model gives realistic values of the RCS which, depending upon the ϕ_{inc} and ϕ_{scat} , can be higher or lower than the mean RCS value. Thus at time

instants, the power level of a certain DT can be lower in the dynamic RCS model. The power level of PC2 in RL-2 is lower in the dynamic RCS integrated model compared to the constant RCS integrated model. This stems from the fact that at $t_{sim} = 3.36$ s, PC2 has a very small RCS value of 0.53 dBsm in the dynamic RCS model. In contrast, for the constant RCS model, PC2 has a constant RCS value of 9.62 dBsm.

Similarly, the power levels of the DT for constant and dynamic RCS integrated models at $t_{sim} = 12.56$ s are compared in Fig. 18b and 18e, respectively. The dynamic RCS integrated model results in a higher power level for DT in L-2 (PC1) than the constant RCS model. This higher power results from the high value of RCS (16.38 dBsm). In contrast, the corresponding RCS value for PC1 in constant RCS integrated model is 9.05 dBsm. At the same time instant, PC2 has a dynamic RCS value of -2.68 dBsm compared to a constant RCS value of 9.63 dBsm. As a result, the power level for the DT in RL-2 (PC2) is lower in the dynamic RCS integrated model compared to the constant RCS integrated model.

In a similar manner, snapshots of target detection at $t_{sim} = 13.38$ s for both models are compared in Fig. 18c and 18f. It can be observed that for the DT in L-0 (bus), the dy-

dynamic RCS integrated model results in a higher power level compared to the constant RCS integrated model. The RCS value for the bus in the dynamic RCS setup is 29.00 dBsm. However, the RCS value for the bus in the constant RCS setup is 14.87 dBsm. This leads to comparatively higher power levels for the DT in the dynamic RCS integrated model. With higher power levels, targets become easier to detect and distinguish from the clutter. The power levels of DI scatterers at $t_{sim} = 13.38$ s are comparatively high as the distance between Rx and Tx is decreased. Although DI scatterers are stationary, they still can have a non-zero Doppler shift depending upon the relative motion of Tx and Rx. This is depicted in Fig. 18c and 18f where the closely located DI scatterers can have higher power levels and varied Doppler shift values.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study investigated the impact of the variable Target Reflectivity (TR) on channel magnitude and target detection in an Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC)-enabled vehicular environment. Furthermore, the impact of vehicle type and geometrical road layouts on the distribution of bistatic TR/ Radar Cross Section (RCS) has also been explored. The variable TR/ dynamic RCS has been integrated into the ISAC-enabled Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) channel model and its performance is compared against the constant TR/ constant RCS integrated model. Our results highlight the significant role of the road layout and vehicle dimensions in the distribution of TR. The variation in TR distribution along the curved road indicates that a robust mechanism is needed to accurately model variable TR. The dynamic RCS integrated model leads to more precise and realistic results by incorporating the orientations of the Transmitter (Tx), Receiver (Rx), and the Dynamic Targets (DT). In contrast, the constant RCS integrated model, which assumes non-varying RCS values, fails to account for this orientation. We have shown through various results that a dynamic RCS integrated model offers a more accurate representation of the target vehicles than a constant RCS integrated model. This study also highlights the importance of including Diffuse (DI) scatterers in propagation modeling as they may present strong clutter making target detection very complicated. As DI scatterers are unavoidable in real-world scenarios, it is essential to account for them in situations where accurate target detection is the primary goal. Therefore, by accurately modeling DI scatterers and having prior knowledge of their positions, we can efficiently suppress clutter echoes using advanced signal processing techniques, enhancing target detection accuracy. This work can be further extended by considering other vehicle models with more diverse TR distribution characteristics. Similarly, other geometrical layouts, such as road intersections and T-shaped configurations can be explored to further assess the influence of vehicle trajectories on target detection accuracy and RCS distribution. Moreover, since only the azimuth plane has been considered, the

elevation plane could also be examined to explore its impact on channel performance and target detection accuracy.

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